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Research Article

**A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON STRESS AND ITS CAUSES
AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS IN PAKISTAN**Dr Ghada Saleem¹, Dr Sara Noreen¹, Dr Hafsa Asif¹¹Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur**Abstract:**

Aims and objectives: The basic aim of the study is to assess the frequency of the stress among the undergraduate students of medical college. **Methodology of the study:** This cross sectional study was conducted at Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur during March 2019 to September 2019. A number of measures were taken to relieve the medical students from stress and depressive symptomatology. For assessment various tools were used i.e. General health questionnaire and Beck's Depression Before the one of exam Kessler10 forms distributed among the undergraduate medical students of 05 years session at college of medicine. Participants obtained all questionnaires. **Results:** The mean age of the study was 22.8±1.3 years. All types of the stress frequency were noted as 59%, while 20.1% severe stress rate was observed. In table 2 there is study variable distribution. 73.3% stress rate was noted in 1st year which is higher as compare to other academic years. 68.8% in 2nd year, 46.30%, 31.50%, 47% were measured for 3rd, 4th and 5th year respectively. **Conclusion:** It is concluded from the results of our study that our educational structure has stressful effect on the student's mental and as well as physical health and the mental health is rapidly deteriorating.

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INTRODUCTION:

Stress is the part and parcel of medical studies. It brings various psychological and social changes among the medical students specially undergraduates. There are emerging patterns of stress in medical students. It seems in different studies that students encounter individual stress amid the course of their medical studies. To secure mastery in scholarly syllabus, negative impacts of stress can prevent it. Different factors like personal or family issues, stress, physical issues etc are faced within the period of medical studies [1]. Eventually, they can influence learning and cognitive capacities of understudies, keeping in view the strict modules of examinations, the pressure is always expanding inferable from unwanted rivalry among the students instead of collaboration and coordination among them [2]. As indicated by an examination, it has been noticed that pressure rises when a student gets admission in Medical institution and subsequently stays poor in his preparation as well. Stress may proceed unabated from school life undergraduate level and then subsequently to the specialist or post graduate level [3].

Aims and objective

The basic aim of the study is to assess the frequency of the stress among the undergraduate students of medical colleges in Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:**Table 1:** Level of stress among Students

Not stressed	41%
Mild	22%
Moderate	17%
Severe	20%

Table 02: Co-relation between stress and the academic years

Academic year	Stress rate	
	No	Yes
1 st year	28 (21.7%)	101 (78.29%)
2 nd year	38 (33.33)	76 (66.66%)
3 rd year	75 (48.07%)	81 (51.92%)
4 th year	50 (64.93%)	27 (35.06%)
5 th year	30 (50.84%)	29 (49.15%)
Academic grading		
Outstanding	95 (42.03%)	131 (57.96%)
Good	56 (48.69%)	59 (51.30%)
Satisfactory	33 (41.77%)	46 (58.22%)
Unsatisfactory	12 (38.70%)	19 (61.29%)
Regular to academic course		
Yes	201 (44.56%)	250 (55.43%)
No	18 (40%)	27 (60%)
Physical issues		
Severe	12 (41.37%)	17 (58.64%)
Mild to moderate	70 (42.68%)	94 (57.31%)
No	106 (38.26%)	277 (61.73%)

This cross sectional study was conducted at Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur during March 2019 to September 2019. For assessment various tools were used i.e. General health questionnaire and Beck's Depression Before the one of exam Kessler10 forms distributed among the undergraduate medical students of 05 years session at college of medicine. Participants obtained all questionnaires. Some extra questions were about the academic achievements, medical health issues in past three weeks, stress source and the number of days with no academic activities.

Statistical analysis

Student's t-test was performed to evaluate the differences in roughness between group P and S. Two-way ANOVA was performed to study the contributions. A chi-square test was used to examine the difference in the distribution of the fracture modes (SPSS 19.0 for Windows, SPSS Inc., USA).

RESULTS:

The mean age of the study was 22.8±1.3 years. All types of the stress frequency were noted as 59%, while 20.1% severe stress rate was observed. In table 2 there is study variable distribution. 73.3% stress rate was noted in 1st year which is higher as compare to other academic years. 68.8% in 2nd year, 46.30%, 31.50%, 47% were measured for 3rd, 4th and 5th year respectively.

DISCUSSION:

This study shows an interesting relationship that decreasing the ratio of stress prevalence with the increasing study years. These results coincide with results of our study that indicates that the stress level is more affected by the grades than the academic years [4]. It has confirmed by other researchers that mental health of students declines after getting admission in medical institutes. It is important to mention here the uniqueness results of our study that shows that the students might have changed behavior and developed a coping mechanism due to our student's support delivery system [5]. Another point is our education here is free of cost and a small stipend is as well granted to the students during the studies. While students of foreign countries may have increased stress level owing to burdensome studies [6]. This is not same in case of colleges as Ministry of education render help the students. Medical studies and its adverse effects have been highlighted by many researchers [7]. A British study has reported that one third students of medicine do not graduate from medical college due to psychological issues [8]. The problems that originate in early stages can be prevented by effective service delivery system of psychological and counselling services. Additionally, lack of social life and pressure of academics can be other reasons. Earlier diagnosis of anxiety and stress and other issues can pose risk of any future complications [9, 10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded from the results of our study that our educational structure has stressful effect on the student's mental and as well as physical health and the mental health is rapidly deteriorating.

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